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RADIATION-INDUCED COMPLICATIONS IN THE PELVIS IN PATIENTS WITH RECTAL CARCINOMA – MR STUDY

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INTRODUCTION: Radiation-induced complications remain a common problem in oncologic patients.

AIM: was to examine differences in type and frequency of radiation-induced changes in the pelvis in patients with rectal cancer (predominantly T3 stage), using MR imaging, who were irradiated in the period 2007-2008 and 2016-2018, on Oncology Institute of Vojvodina.

MATERIALS AND METHODS: Patients were divided into two groups (2007-2008 the first group and 2016-2018, the second group). In the first group there were 21 patients (6 females and 15 males), average age 60 years, with dose of 50,4Gy/28 fractions. In the second group there were 30 patients (5 females and 25 males), average age 61 years, with dose of 25Gy/5fractions to 45Gy/25fractions+9Gy/5fractions. The presence and frequency of radiation-induced complications were compared in two groups, comprising: fat bone metaplasia, edema of rectal mucosa, edema of the bladder wall, edema in soft tissues, fistulas, ascites, prostatic changes, fibrosis of the seminal vesicles and osteoradiation necrosis. Statistical analysis was performed using chi-square test, with significance vaule set at $p < 0.05$.

RESULTS: In the first group, we observed bone fat metaplasia in 90% of patients (19/21), edema of rectal mucosa in 33% (7/21), edema of the bladder wall in 29% (6/21), edema of soft tissues in 33% (7/21), fistulas in 19% (4/21), ascites in 19% (4/21), prostatic changes in 27% (4/16), fibrosis of the seminal vesicles in 7% (1/16) and osteoradiation necrosis in 13% of patients (3/21).

In the second group, we observed bone fat metaplasia in 80% of patients (24/30), edema of rectal mucosa in 57% (17/30), edema of the

bladder wall in 27% (8/30), edema of the soft tissues in 27% (8/30), fistulas in 13% (4/30), ascites in 3% (1/30), prostatic changes in 6%(9/25), fibrosis of the seminal vesicles in 24% (6/24) and osteoradiation necrosis in 20% (6/30) of patients.

CONCLUSION: There were no significant differences in the type and frequency of detected radiation-induced changes in patients with rectal cancer, detected on MR imaging, in the patients who underwent radiation therapy in two different time periods in our institution.